

The protease MBTPS2 is an important regulator of several cellular processes, especially in health and sickness

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Abstract- Since the identification of MBTPS2 in 1997, tremendous progress has been made in determining the protease's functions. The protease has developed from an element of the SREBP cleavage machinery to an important regulator of several cellular processes, especially in health and sickness. With this newfound information from biochemical and structural biology, S2P's proteolytic action through peptide bond hydrolysis can occur in the membrane, providing a conceptual framework for appreciating S2P's roles in other aspects, and showing that many other substrates rely on S2P for their survival. In addition, we discovered the identity of both of S2P's catalytic active sites, an essential finding as the activity of the proteolysis as well as the pathogenesis of MBTPS2-caused illnesses seems to be connected to the molecular and biochemical features of the catalytic sites. Additionally, MBTPS2 causes different diseases, possibly illustrating the pleiotropic nature of the protein. Also, while the ailments reported thus far are all due to mutations that cause MBTPS2 to lose function, other variants that cause MBTPS2 to be hyperactive have not been examined. Nevertheless, recognizing the related sickness pathomechanism is a challenge. Pursuing these challenging technical areas would most definitely enhance our understanding of MBTPS2 in disease states. MBTPS2 appears to be nearing the solution to many of the remaining fundamental questions surrounding the mechanism of its action, as well as being a therapeutic target for new therapies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Site-2 protease (S2P) is an integral membrane protein that regulates membrane-tethered transcriptional factors and is encoded by the Membrane-Bound Transcription Factor Protease, Site-2 gene (MBTPS2) on the X-chromosome. It is found across the Golgi membrane, where it works in tandem with site-1 protease (S1P), which is encoded by membrane-bound transcription factor protease, site-1 (MBTPS1), to proteolytically activate membrane-tethered latent transcription factors. Regulated intramembrane proteolysis is the name for this process (RIP). RIP is a well-organized process that regulates a variety of processes including cellular division and differentiation, cell migration, transcriptional regulation, apoptosis, cellular stress responses, degradation of transmembrane protein fragments, and lipid metabolism, as well as a variety of physiological processes such as embryonic development. RIP disruption or dysregulation has been linked to the development of a number of illnesses, including cancer, Alzheimer's disease, and developmental problems (2,3,4).

A two-step sequential cleavage method is commonly used in RIP. The first cleavage, which occurs either spontaneously or in response to cell stimuli, cleaves a membrane protein substrate close to or within its transmembrane (TM), releasing the soluble extracellular domain (ectodomain) from the membrane while leaving a fragment with one or more functional domains bound to the membrane (5). A second protease recognizes the remaining membrane-embedded fragment and cleaves it within the TM region, releasing the fragment into the cytoplasm. The fragment is either translocated to the nucleus, where it works as a transcription regulator (2) or works as a signaling pathway activator (6) once it is released.

The aspartyl protease-like, zinc metalloproteinase S2P, serine protease family of rhomboids, and glutamatergic intramembrane proteases are the four unique and evolutionarily conserved intramembrane cleaving proteases (I-CLiPs) that release membrane bound fragments into the cytosol (7). The S2P was the first of the four I-CLiPs to be found, having a role in modulating the activity of the membrane-bound transcription factors sterol regulator element binding proteins (SREBPs) in the feedback regulation of sterol and fatty acid production and absorption (8,9,10). Other transcriptional factors, such as activating transcription factor 6 (ATF6) (11) and cyclic AMP-responsive element-binding protein 3-like protein 3 (CREB3L3) (12), were later discovered for other pathways. MBTPS2 (MIM # 300,294) has recently been given new roles, not only in terms of the transcription factors it processes, but also in terms of its involvement in unexpected pathways that are important for a variety of biological processes, such as ER stress, unfolded protein response, and gluconeogenesis (13). As a result, MBTPS2 plays a role

discovered in organogenesis and tissue homeostasis (25,26,27).

Cyclic-AMP responsive element-binding protein 3 is a protein that binds to cyclic-AMP responsive elements (CREB3). CREB3, CREB3L1, CREB3L2, CREB3L3, and CREB3L4 are the five members of the CREB3 transcription factor family. All members of this family, including SREBPs and ATF6, have a single TM helix with an NH₂-terminal cytosolic domain that resembles a bZIP transcription factor and is proteolytically cleaved by S1P and S2P. They are known to play important functions in development, but they also play functions in metabolism, signaling protein production, cell survival, differentiation and division, and cancer.

CREB3 or Luman was the first member of its family to be discovered as an ER-bound transcription factor (28, 29), acting as a parallel to the herpes simplex virus transcriptional activator VP16, which binds to the host cell factor regulator. It is now well understood to be involved in ER stress and unfolded protein responses, as well as having regulatory roles in a variety of processes such as dendritic cell maturation (30), Golgi stress (31), glucocorticoid receptor signaling (32), leukocyte migration and function (33, 34), and breast cancer metastatic progression (35). Following stimulation, CREB3 is transported to the Golgi, where it is cleaved by S1P and S2P in a sequential order. The released NH₂-terminal portion travels to the nucleus, where it activates target transcription genes and proteins such as the cAMP response element (CRE), the ER stress response element II, and the unfolded protein response element (36, 37). Transient translational retardation, transcription start of ER-resident chaperone folding capacity, and destruction of accumulated unfolded proteins in the ER occur as a result of activation, limiting cellular damage and apoptotic cell death (36).

CREB3L1, formerly known as OASIS, is important for bone growth. CREB3L1 is cleaved progressively by S1P and S2P in response to bone morphogenetic protein-2 (BMP-2), a cytokine needed for bone production and osteoblast development (38, 39). The cleaved NH₂-terminal fragment reaches the nucleus and binds to a CRE-like motif in COL1A1's promoter region to start transcription. Its contribution as a hereditary cause of OI (40,41,42) bolstered its major position in bone development. Genes encoding components of the COPII coat, Sec23A and Sec24, protein components important for the transport and secretion of cartilage matrix proteins from the rough ER to the Golgi apparatus, were downregulated by CREB3L1 mutations (43).

CREB3L2 is found in a variety of tissues and organs, although it is particularly abundant in proliferating chondrocytes in cartilage (39, 43). S1P and S2P cleave CREB3L2 in the Golgi during chondrocyte proliferation. CREB3L2's NH₂-terminal domain then reaches the nucleus and induces the transcription of SEC23A and SEC24 genes (43). The transcription of these genes causes the COPII-coated vesicles to enlarge in order to accept the bulky type II collagen, which is required for chondrogenesis and differentiation (44). CREB3L2 is also thought to have a function in increasing collagen production in dermal fibroblasts through the Sec23A pathway (45).

CREB3L3, also known as CREB-H, was shown to be a hepatocyte-specific bZIP transcription factor that plays a key role in innate immunity (12, 46). Following microbial infection, leukocytes produce pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-6 (IL-6) that cause ER stress in hepatocytes, which causes S1P and S2P to proteolytically cleave CREB3L3 (12). The cleaved NH₂-terminal nuclear form increases C-reactive protein and other acute phase proteins transcription in the liver, allowing for an early response to microbial infection (12, 47). On the contrary, recent research demonstrated that the proteolytic cleavage of CREB3L3 in response to the generation of proinflammatory cytokines during myocardial ischemia induces myocardial cell damage (48).

CREB3L3 has also been linked to the suppression of osteogenesis caused by ER stress and the proinflammatory cytokine TNF. Cleaved CREB3L3 blunted the BMP-2-induced up-regulation of osteogenic markers runt-related transcription factor 2 (RUNX2), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), and osteocalcin in both MC3T3-E1 cells, a murine preosteoblast cell line, and primary osteoblasts after the induction of tunicamycin, a potent inducer of ER stress, and TNF. This points to CREB3L3 having a detrimental impact on osteoblast development and bone production (49, 50). Interestingly, despite their tight relationship, BMP-2 has the opposite impact on CREB3L1. CREB3L3 was discovered to play a function in osteoclastogenesis in another investigation. The accumulation of activated CREB3L3 in the nucleus and the activation of the inflammatory transcription factor nuclear factor of activated T cells (NFATC1), a prominent transcription factor for osteoclast differentiation, resulted from the differentiation of osteoclast precursor cells via receptor activator of NF- κ B ligand (RANKL)-induced differentiation. However, inhibiting ER stress lowered the expression of osteoclast-related genes and CREB3L3 activation, preventing RANKL-induced bone degradation, suggesting that inactivating ER stress CREB3L3-induced signaling pathways might be useful in the treatment of osteoporosis (51).

CREB3L4, also known as androgen-induced bZIP protein (AibZIP), is prevalent in the prostate and has a role in spermiogenesis chromatin architecture (52,53,54). CREB3L4, like other members of the CREB3 family, has a single TM helix with an NH₂-terminal cytosolic domain that looks like a bZIP transcription factor. However, unlike its cousins, the necessity for its activation to be cleaved sequentially by S1P and S2P at the Golgi remains a little unclear. Treatment of the human prostate cancer cell line LNCaP with brefeldin A, a pharmacological drug that compresses the ER and Golgi into a single compartment, resulted in lower levels of full-length CREB3L4, demonstrating that CREB3L4 undergoes S1P and S2P cleavage at the Golgi (55). However, in a more recent work, CREB3L4 was shown to be localized to both the Golgi apparatus and the ER, indicating that it was not proteolytically cleaved by S1P and S2P in both normal and ER-stressed LNCaP cells (56). The

activation of CREB3L4 may consequently necessitate the proteolytic cleavage of additional components or triggers. Despite this, CREB3L4 has been related to a variety of cellular processes other than spermiogenesis, including cellular differentiation into adipocytes (57) and breast cancer development (58).

III. MBTPS2 PROTEIN STRUCTURE AND GENE

As previously stated, MBTPS2's principal purpose is to cleave its substrates so that they can conduct essential cellular processes. MBTPS2 does this by utilizing both of its conserved catalytic site motifs, HExxH and LDG, which are not only unique to MBTPS2 but also essential to its function. The structural investigations of MBTPS2, conducted using sequence-based topology predictions or X-ray crystallography techniques, have revealed a great deal about MBTPS2's core structural needs and how they conform to its function as a membrane-embedded protease.

The MBTPS2 gene contains 11 exons and spans more than 4 kilobase pairs on human chromosome X. A combination of protease protection and glycosylation experiments indicated that MBTPS2 is 519 amino acids long and has a primary structure consisting of eight TM helices partitioned by four luminal loops and two cytoplasmic domains, an NH₂- and a COOH-terminal (18). The core portions of MBTPS2 are found in the fourth (TM4) and seventh (TM7) transmembrane domains, which include both of its conserved catalytic motifs, HExxH and LDG, respectively. The HExxH pattern is a well-known zinc metalloprotease signature that involves two histidine residues chelating a catalytic zinc ion and a glutamate residue activating a water molecule for peptide bond hydrolysis. The aspartate residue in the LDG motif, another hallmark pattern of metalloproteases, aids in the coordination of the zinc ion (18, 59). Following S1P cleavage, these residues activate a zinc-bound molecule, which launches a nucleophilic assault on a substrate's scissile peptide bond.

The charged amino acids lysine, arginine, glutamate, and aspartate are distributed unevenly in the luminal loops (18). Apart from its hydrophilicity, the first luminal loop is unimpressive. The second loop has 76 percent serine residues, yet the significance of this sequence of serine residues is unknown. The longest of the loops, the third, has a PDZ domain with a cysteine-rich insert, charged and polar amino acids, and a consensus sequence with homology to a glycosylated region, with 188 residues. Unlike MBTPS1, which needs fragmentation of its inhibitory component prior to activation, protein glycosylation has not been indicated as a required posttranslational alteration for MBTPS2 activation or function (60). The PDZ domain, on the other hand, has been proposed to be crucial in the recognition and/or binding of a newly produced COOH-terminus end of substrates after S1P cleavage (61). As a result, the existence of a PDZ domain might explain why a substrate must be cleaved by S1P before being cleaved by S2P (62). PDZ domains are found on the COOH-terminal of bacterial S2P homologs and are thought to be important for substrate recognition. In *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, for example, removing the PDZ binding domain of Rip1 (S2P) by COOH-terminal truncation inhibited Rip1 from binding to PDZ-interacting protease regulator 1. As a result, the PDZ binding domain functions as a substrate-specific adaptor protein, tethering the substrate to S2P for cleavage and release in the cytosol (63). The human S2P's utilization of the PDZ domain as a substrate-specific adaptor protein has yet to be proved, therefore it's still a work in progress. Before the protein finishes at its COOH-terminal, the fourth luminal loop, the smallest of the loops, crosses the final TM helix.

Sequence homologs investigations (61, 64) have recently verified this expected architectural perspective of the MBTPS2 structure, as has the first S2P atomic-resolution crystal structure derived from an archaeobacterium S2P (*Methanocaldococcus jannaschii* S2P (MjS2P)) (65). Despite the fact that the human S2P projected sequence topology and the crystal structure of MjS2P were acquired from the archaeal S2P homolog, there are notable similarities between the human S2P projected sequence topology and the crystal structure of MjS2P. First, the two catalytic active sites are located on the cytosolic side of the membrane. This orientation, interestingly, corresponds to where SREBPs are cleaved, which is towards the cytosolic region of the membrane (8, 66).

Second, the geometry of the active-site residues, the placement of the catalytic dyad, His-His and Asp for catalytic activity, and the spatial arrangement of the HExxH-containing metalloproteases, such as thermolysin (67), all coordinate with each other and are spatially arranged in a manner similar to that seen with other HExxH-containing metalloprotease. The main difference is that the MjS2P crystal structure implies a six-TM helix model, which we believe is related to the fact that the human S2P is longer than the MjS2P.

For the first time, the MjS2P crystal structure has provided unparalleled structural and mechanistic insights into S2P at the atomic level, bringing solutions to difficult issues and unique discoveries. The topic of how a water-requiring proteolytic process may proceed in a lipid membrane has been a long-standing enigma of S2P proteolysis, and indeed of most intramembrane proteases. The structure revealed the presence of a polar channel at the COOH-terminal that allows water to enter S2P's active sites. The inner surface of the polar channel is also coated with many polar groups and charged amino acids, such as backbone carbonyls and acidic and basic side chains, which creates an aqueous milieu that is necessary for proteolysis. The structure also indicated that proteolysis takes place inside the plane of the membrane, as the catalytic active site residues were discovered under the membrane's surface. Another fascinating finding is evidence of a lateral gating mechanism that controls substrate access to active catalytic sites. The S2P active sites are exposed by moving TM1 and TM6 apart from each other in a "double door opening" fashion. This helical translocation creates a cleft as broad as the length S2P, which is large enough to accept the substrate (65). This mechanism is very comparable to that seen in the crystal structures of other membrane proteases, such as rhomboids (68). As a result, we may begin to sketch a picture of MBTPS2's basic catalytic processes, which might serve as a conceptual foundation for a

better understanding of the machinery that drives its proteolytic activity. However, because this gating mechanism was derived from an archaeal S2P homolog, it is uncertain if it will be relevant for human MBTPS2, and it is unlikely to be fully resolved until complexes of S2P bound to a substrate can be crystallized and their structure identified.

The effective resolution of the MjS2P structure may have dispelled previous suspicions about MBTPS2's proteolysis activity, but it has also raised new issues. One component in particular has yet to be determined: how substrates unfold or unwind to provide MBTPS2's catalytic sites access to the scissile peptide bond. The cleavage of SREBPs can be used as a template: once S1P cleaves SREBPs at their luminal loop, both of its TM segments split, permitting it to partly unfurl and its transcriptional domain to be easily reached by S2P (59). Because the specific method of cleavage for the other MBTPS2 substrates, such as ATF6 and CREB3, is unknown, it can only be assumed that these substrates must be unfolded in order for their scissile peptide bond to be exposed to MBTPS2 catalytic sites. Another area where we don't have a lot of information is how MBTPS2 substrates are specified or chosen. Two regions were discovered to be important for S2P cleavage in early mutational investigations of SREBPs (59).

The first is Asp-Arg-Ser-Arg (DRSR), which comes before SREBP-1a and SREBP-2's first TM segment. S2P cleavage for SREBP-1a was substantially affected by changes to the DRSR sequence via substitutions or deletions, but not for SREBP-2. The second critical sequence for S2P cleavage is Asn-Pro (NP), which is found inside SREBP-2's first TM segment. Alterations to each NP residue resulted in a partial decrease of S2P cleavage, whereas changes to both sequences at the same time totally prevented S2P cleavage of SREBP-2. Translocating the NP sequence 5 residues NH2-terminally had no effect on the site of cleavage or the ability of S2P to cleave it (59). Because it is not spatially restricted, this might represent a recognition sequence. It was not known, however, if cleavage at a different site had any downstream consequences, such as at the transcriptional level. Similarly, ATF6's TM domain has an Asn-Tyr-Gly-Pro (NYGP) sequence that is crucial for S2P cleavage, since replacement of both NP residues entirely prevented cleavage (11). The existence of the NP sequence in SREBP-2 and ATF6 is an interesting discovery of a specific recognition sequence that can determine MBTPS2 substrate specificity rather than merely a sequence cleavage, but it requires more investigation. The PDZ domain on the COOH-terminal of MBTPS2 might be another pathway for a regulatory mechanism, especially given the fact that many bacteria S2P use their PDZ binding motif as an adaptor protein for substrate specificity. The MjS2P, on the other hand, did not have any domain or motif inserted between its TMS and luminal loop, but did have a very prominent hole in its structure, which we are tempted to assume is where the PDZ binding motif would lie.

Overall, these developing theories seem credible, but more research is needed into the specifics of S2P substrate entrance, its catalytic mechanism, and the criteria of what constitutes an S2P substrate. Perhaps genome editing techniques like CRISPR-Cas9 of known substrates paired with structures of S2P in combination with its substrates can help solve this. The implications of these findings will be of great interest not just on a mechanistic and theoretical level, but also in terms of understanding how MBTPS2 works in diverse biological situations, disorders, and the potential for using MBTPS2 and its substrates as a therapeutic target.

IV. DISEASES LINKED TO MBTPS2

Given MBTPS2's importance in cholesterol homeostasis and ER stress responses, as well as the numerous substrates and cellular activities that rely on its proteolytic activity, it's not unexpected that MBTPS2 loss can result in a variety of illnesses. Mutations in the MBTPS2 gene have been linked to a variety of severe conditions, including IFAP syndrome with or without BRESHECK, KFSD, Olmsted, and, most recently, OI.

IFAP syndrome (ichthyosis follicularis, alopecia, and photophobia) with or without BRESHECK

Since it was initially recognized by McLeod in 1909 (69), IFAP syndrome (MIM # 308205) is an exceptionally rare congenital condition, with just around 60 instances known globally. The condition is inherited in an X-linked recessive manner and mostly affects men; however, autosomal-dominantly inherited IFAP instances have been reported in females (70,71,72). Female carriers have been found to show symptoms such as follicular ichthyosis, moderate atrophoderma, hairlessness, and hypohidrosis in a linear mosaic pattern, albeit the characteristic may be nonpenetrant or minor (73, 74). The clinical spectrum of this disease in males varies, ranging from moderate to severe, but all afflicted people have the strange triad of follicular ichthyosis, non-scarring widespread hair loss, and aberrant light sensitivity (75). The defining characteristic of this condition is ichthyosis follicularis, which manifests as extensive non-inflammatory thorn-like follicular keratosis, which commonly affects the scalp and extensor limbs. Hyperkeratotic psoriasiform plaques, lamellar scaling, angular cheilitis, periungual inflammation, and dystrophic nails are all possible cutaneous abnormalities. Hair loss at the scalp, eyebrows, and eyelashes, as well as whole body hair loss, are the most common symptoms of non-cicatricial alopecia. Superficial corneal ulceration and vascularization create gradual scarring of the cornea and may result in a Bowman membrane defect, which causes photophobia, the triad's third distinguishing feature. Corneal erosions and scarring, chronic tearing, nystagmus, myopia, and atopic keratoconjunctivitis are further ocular symptoms. There is no effect on the anterior chamber, lens, or ocular fundus. Intellectual incapacity, seizures, hypotonia, short stature, frontal bossing, choanal atresia, recurrent infections, and intestinal abnormalities, as well as renal, cardiac, and spinal defects, may occur in conjunction with the triad (76). Brain anomalies, intellectual disability, ectodermal dysplasia, skeletal deformities, ear or eye anomalies, and renal anomalies or small kidneys, with or without Hirschsprung disease and cleft palate or cryptorchidism (BRESEK or BRESHECK) can all be seen in affected individuals in extreme cases (77).

The genetic foundation of this uncommon condition was just discovered in 2009 (78), despite the fact that it was first reported over a century ago in 1909. Five unrelated afflicted individuals with the IFAP syndrome were each discovered to have a missense mutation in MBTPS2 after linkage analysis and sequencing of the candidate genes. The five discovered missense variants, p.R429H, p.H227L, p.M87I, p.W226L, and p.F475S, all abolished S2P proteolytic activity, with the level of S2P proteolytic activity loss being unique to each mutation. This was determined by examining cell viability in M19 CHO cells with the various missense mutations found. The five mutants showed various degrees of poor cell development under sterol-depleted conditions as compared to M19 cells transfected with wild-type MBTPS2. The p.R429H mutant, which had essentially no measurable cell growth and the lowest residual proteolytic activity, was the most startling. Surprisingly, the afflicted man with this mutation also exhibited the most significant IFAP symptoms, indicating a link between clinical severity and the level of S2P proteolytic function impairment caused by the mutation (78).

This mutation is found in the COOH-terminal domain, which is positioned near the LDG motif at TM 7, one of S2P's two proteolytic active sites, implying a link between proteolytic function and clinical severity.

In terms of genotype–phenotype connection, mutations in or around TM 5 and 8 appear to cause severe symptoms, whereas mutations closer to the NH₂-or COOH-terminals cause milder types of IFAP. This is true not only for the p.R429H mutation, but also for the p.L433P, p.A454P, p.F475S, p.L476S, p.D477V, p.A478D, and p.G500D mutations, all of which are located near the LDG motif and cause clinically severe IFAP abnormalities (78,79,80,81). Furthermore, mutations in the TM 5, such as p.F229S, p.W226L, p.H227L, p.G253A, and p.I258M, are linked to severe IFAP phenotypes. The afflicted man had characteristic clinical symptoms of IFAP, including psoriasiform skin plaques, nail dystrophy, facial dysmorphism, intellectual impairment, severe skeletal deformities, and chorea-like movement, as well as a mutation at the big luminal loop between TM 6 and 7 (p.C334Y). Though the IFAP symptoms of this mutation were not severe, it might indicate that a mutation at this location is associated with severe skeletal abnormalities. This, however, has to be explained (82). A patient with the p.L24P mutation, which is located towards the NH₂-terminal end of TM 1, displayed modest IFAP symptoms as well as overall developmental delay (83). IFAP symptoms were milder in two other individuals, one with the p.M87I mutation, the second most-proximal mutation on TM 2, and the other with the p.L513P mutation, the most COOH-terminal mutation on TM 8 (78, 79). Nonetheless, it might be argued that mutation sites can not be used to construct a precise phenotypic or genotype association. In one investigation, a patient with the p.R429H mutation showed moderate IFAP symptoms, in contrast to what had previously been observed; nonetheless, the patient did have neurological abnormalities such as delayed psychomotor development and seizures (78, 84). Another patient was afflicted by BRESHECK with atrichia and photophobia rather than the IFAP triad (85). Another patient had the cardinal triad of IFAP plus five additional BRESHECK characteristics (77). As a result, when predicting the clinical consequences of a certain mutation, care must be exercised.

Initially, Reish et al. (1997) classified BRESEK or BRESHECK as a separate entity called 'BRESEK or BRESHECK syndrome; however, because the majority of its symptoms are often seen in conjunction with the IFAP triad, particularly Hirschsprung disease in severe cases of IFAP, IFAP, and BRESHECK have been grouped together as 'IFAP with or without BRESHECK (MIM # 308205) (77,78,79). In essence, Martino et al. (1992) reported a male patient with the IFAP triad and additional symptoms that were very similar to those of the BRESHECK syndrome, including short stature, intellectual disability, seizures, hypohidrosis, enamel dysplasia, congenital aganglionic megacolon, inguinal hernia, vertebral and renal fusion.

Keratitis follicularis spinulosa decalvans is a kind of keratitis follicularis.

Keratitis follicularis spinulosa decalvans (KFSD, MIM # 308800) is an uncommon keratinization condition characterized by hyperkeratotic follicular papules (87). The condition, which was first described in 1926, is most commonly seen in infancy or early childhood and is inherited in an X-linked pattern, while sporadic occurrences or instances inherited in an autosomal dominant pattern have been recorded (88,89,90,91,92). Symptoms include keratitis pilaris-like papules, facial erythema, hypotrichosis, and cicatricial alopecia of the scalp, eyebrows, and eyelashes in some people. Photophobia, keratitis, blepharitis, and enamel hypoplasia are all extracutaneous characteristics. Because the phenotypes of this illness closely resemble those of IFAP, it is frequently referred to as a "milder version of IFAP." However, KFSD differs from IFAP due to the nature of the alopecia, which is progressive with varying degrees of inflammatory change leading to scarring in KFSD.

MBTPS2 mutations have been identified as one of the KFSD causal genes. Mutations that cause KFSD, like those that cause the IFAP triad, are found in MBTPS2's TM domains. A missense mutation in MBTPS2 (p.N508S) was discovered in afflicted men with modest symptoms in three unrelated families (87). Following that, two separate investigations found that the identical mutation was associated with moderate KFSD symptoms in a Chinese and a Swedish family (79, 92). The location of this recurrent mutation was determined to be at MBTPS2's COOH-terminal end, and a genotype–phenotype impact specific to the MBTPS2 mutation was proposed. Indeed, cell viability studies of M19 CHO cells with the p.N508S mutation indicated a 50% reduction in growth rate under sterol deficient circumstances compared to wild-type. The p.N508S mutant had a greater survival rate than the mutations producing severe symptoms of IFAP (78, 79, 87). This not only supports the idea that mutations far from the active proteolytic site do not cause severe symptoms, but it also suggests that mutation localisation might be used as a measure of clinical severity (78). Following that, other missense MBTPS2 mutations have been associated with moderate KFSD symptoms and follow the genotype to phenotype pattern (79, 93, 94).

Olmsted syndrome

Olmsted syndrome (OS, MIM # 614594) is a keratinization hereditary condition that is characterized by bilateral mutilating palmoplantar keratoderma and periorificial hyperkeratotic plaques (95). The illness usually appears at birth or in early infancy, although it has also been recorded in adults (96). The clinical appearance of bilateral mutilating palmoplantar keratoderma and periorificial hyperkeratotic plaques is used to diagnose OS, albeit there is a wide range of phenotypic spectrum due to the presence of associated characteristics. Squamous cell carcinomas, corneal opacities, widespread alopecia, digital constriction rings, nail dystrophy, high-tone hearing impairment, infections, hyperkeratotic linear streaks at the elbows, knees, axillae, and antecubital fossae, and infections. As a result, diagnosis is sometimes challenging and perplexing because the bulk of its phenotypes coincide with those of IFAP. In addition to the canonical OS-causing gene, transient receptor potential cation channel, subfamily V (TRPV3), and MBTPS2 mutations have recently been found to cause OS via an X-linked mode of inheritance (74, 99,100,101,102,103,104).

Three of the 106 instances of OS have so far been linked to mutations in the MBTPS2 gene. The first is a missense mutation (p.F464S) that two men with an Iranian pedigree have (99, 105). This missense mutation is found on TM 7, just two codons from MBTPS2's LDG catalytic site. Severe OS symptoms were predicted since the motif was so near to the LDG motif. As a result, the two probands had severe alopecia universalis, painful hyperkeratotic lesions, severe periorificial plaques, and highly dystrophic yellow-colored nails with a fork-like shape. A c.671-9 T > G intronic mutation was discovered in a Chinese proband with short stature, inguinal hernia, palmoplantar, periorificial keratoderma, and pachyonychia, as well as the IFAP triad of short stature, inguinal hernia, palmoplantar, periorificial keratoderma, and pachyonychia in another pedigree (74). This mutation was previously described in two IFAP patients who also had hernias, small stature, and thicker dystrophic nails but no OS symptoms (78). The intronic splicing enhancer was disrupted by this mutation, which resulted in the skipping of exon 6 for mRNA transcription and a frameshift that caused MBTPS2 (p.I225Lfs * 25) to be prematurely terminated (74, 78). This broadens the range of MBTPS2 mutations to include not only those affecting the TM domains but also those affecting the exon-intron boundaries. The third mutation (p.F475S) is a recurrent mutation that has been found in two Lebanese brothers who have clinical symptoms of both OS and IFAP (104). This missense mutation has previously been reported in an Argentinian man and two Lebanese brothers with severe IFAP symptoms including hyperkeratotic psoriasis-like lesions and plantar keratoderma, among other things (78, 79), but no mention of OS. In another study, Nemer et al. (2017) found that two afflicted Lebanese brothers had both IFAP and OS characteristics, including developmental delays, recurrent seizures, osteoporosis, and renal insufficiency (104). The difficulty in achieving a diagnosis when OS patients with IFAP signs or vice versa are presented at the same time is highlighted by these publications. As a result, there is debate on whether X-linked OS should be considered a distinct syndrome or simply a severe form of IFAP (74, 106). The basis for the dispute stems from the fact that people with clinical characteristics of OS can also have IFAP phenotypes. This is in contrast to the beginning of OS caused by TRPV3 mutations, which results in afflicted people displaying solely traditional OS characteristics and no IFAP symptoms. Further research is needed to determine if OS should be classified with IFAP in the same way as the BRESHECK condition was classed as "IFAP with or without BRESHECK."

Osteogenesis imperfecta (OI), often known as brittle bone disease, is a congenital heterogeneous skeletal deformity illness that affects 1 in 10,000–20,000 infants globally (107). Individuals with OI have a distinct skeletal phenotype with a wide range of clinical severity, ranging from low bone mass to increasing bone abnormalities with increased fracture frequency and infant fatality. OI patients may also have a variety of secondary characteristics such as craniofacial abnormalities, scoliosis, atraumatic subluxations, and dentinogenesis imperfecta, as well as extra-skeletal symptoms like as hearing loss, blue sclerae, and lung abnormalities (108, 109).

OI is usually caused by autosomal dominant mutations in either the COL1A1 or COL1A2 genes that encode for collagen type 1 alpha chains, resulting in a change in the structure or function of collagen type 1, the most abundant protein in bone extracellular matrix (108, 110,111,112). As a result of autosomal recessive inheritance, mutations in genes involved in posttranslational modification of collagen (CRTAP, PPIB, LEPRE1/P3H1) (113,114,115), folding (SERPINH1, FKBP10) (13, 116), intracellular trafficking (SEC24D) (117), and extracellular processing (BMP1) (118, 119) have also been reported to cause OI. The introduction of high-resolution sequencing methods like as next-generation sequencing (NGS) and the rising use of whole-exome sequencing over the last decade, however, has substantially expanded the horizon of genetic contributions to OI. These methods have led to the discovery of new OI-causing genes and novel pathogenic variants that are not traditionally associated with collagen metabolism and can manifest themselves in different ways, such as the first X-linked recessive form of OI (OI type XIX, OI19, MIM # 301014), which is caused by missense mutations in MBTPS2 (3, 120, 121). Linkage analysis and NGS identified two unique MBTPS2 missense variants in two distinct pedigrees with moderate to severe OI. The resultant mutations (p.N459S and p.L505F) were discovered inside or near the zinc ion coordinating site essential for enzymatic function in both pedigrees. Although mutant S2P expression levels remained steady, processing of the RIP substrates ATF6, CREB3L3, and SREBPs was hindered, resulting in lower expression levels of numerous genes important for osteoblast development and extracellular matrix formation.

An in-depth characterization of intracellular signaling differences associated with skin disorders or OI mutations using stem cell-based disease models such as induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) and/or animal models may potentially reveal the underlying molecular mechanism for the phenotypic differences for these very distinct disorders (122). Any insights acquired from these investigations will help us better understand MBTPS2's qualities in illness and, as a result, aid in the development of MBTPS2 as a therapeutic target for the treatment of skin diseases and

Ol. Nelfinavir, an HIV protease inhibitor, has been shown to cause apoptosis and growth arrest in both liposarcoma and castration-resistant prostate cancer cells by inhibiting S2P activity (123,124,125-274), suggesting that S2P might be used as a therapeutic target for some cancers.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Since the unexpected discovery of MBTPS2 in 1997, enormous progress has been made in gaining a better grasp of the functions of this formerly controversial protease. S2P has evolved from a component of the SREBP cleavage machinery to a protease that is now generally recognized as a crucial regulator of a variety of cellular activities in health and illness. Biochemical and structural biology studies have provided spectacular insights into the mechanisms and functions of S2P, resolving the long-standing question of whether its proteolytic action via peptide bond hydrolysis can occur in the membrane, providing a conceptual platform for appreciating S2P's broader functions, and revealing a plethora of substrates that are completely reliant on S2P for their survival.

Another important finding is the identification of both of S2P's catalytic active sites, which is not only important for its proteolysis but also appears to be an important factor in the pathogenesis of disorders caused by MBTPS2 mutations, as several studies have found a strong correlation between the molecular and biochemical properties of the mutations to the catalytic sites. What's more, the extremely diverse pathologies caused by MBTPS2 variations are rather remarkable, which might indicate that MBTPS2 has pleiotropic features. Furthermore, while the illnesses that have been described so far all result from mutations that cause MBTPS2 to lose function, an area that has not been explored is the consequences or diseases of variations that cause MBTPS2 hyperactivity. Nonetheless, comprehending the complicated pathomechanism underlying the linked different illnesses remains a problem. Putting more effort into these critical, if difficult, technical areas will undoubtedly advance our understanding of MBTPS2 under pathophysiological situations. Looking ahead, we expect that many of the remaining fundamental concerns concerning MBTPS2 will be answered, and we anticipate exciting breakthroughs in both the mechanistic aspects of MBTPS2 activity and its use as a therapeutic target.

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